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INGLIZ TILIDA SO'Z YASALISHINING BA'ZI USULLARI VA USLUBLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ingliz tili hozirgi kunga kelib butun jahonda keng miqyosda o'rganilayotgan tillardan biriga aylanib ulgurishi bilan birgalikda shuningdek u professional jihatdan ham oliy ta'lim muassalarida ham tadqiq qilinmoqda. Leksikologiya – ingliz tilining shunday sohalaridan biriki, unda tilning leksika masalasi turli tomonlardan o'rganiladi. So'z yasalishi muammosi ham uning tadqiqot sohalaridan biri sanaladi. Quyidagi maqola so'z yasalishi turlari va uslublariga bag'ishlangan bo'lib, o'z navbatida tilning boyish manbalarini ko'rib chiqadi.

Kalit so'zlar: morfema, o'zak, qo'shimcha, suffiks, prefix, konversiya, so'z qo'shish, qisqartmalar.

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НЕКОТОРЫЕ ВИДЫ И СПОСОБЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ СЛОВ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Английский язык стал одним из интенсивно изучаемых языков во всем мире, и его также преподают профессионально в образовательных учреждениях как институты и университеты. Лексикология – это одна из отраслей английского языка, изучающая лексику языка с разных точек зрения. Проблема словообразования также является одной из ее задач. Следующая статья посвящена её типам и способам образования новых слов, которые в свою очередь способствуют обогащению языка.

Ключевые слова: морфема, корень, аффиксы, суффикс, префикс, конверсия, словосочетание, аббревиатуры.

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SOME PATTERNS AND MEANS OF FORMING WORDS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

ANNOTATION

English has become one of the intensively learned languages around the world and it has been taught professionally as well in higher educational establishments. Lexicology is one of the branches of English language, which investigates lexicon of the language from various perspectives. The issue of word formation is also one of its targets. Following article deals with types of it and the ways of forming new words.

Key words: morpheme, root, affix, suffix, prefix, conversion, composition, shortenings.

Before investigating different methods of forming words, we think it will be beneficial to explore the problem connected, that is its structural components.

From the point of the structure, words are divided into smaller items - morphemes. They are not necessarily found as independent forms; however they can come as a structural part of a word. Still, morphemes do have their own meaning. [5,278]

All morphemes, on their turn, create two big subdivisions such as roots or radicals and affixes. The second, in its turn, is subdivided into prefixes and suffixes. Prefixes are the type of affixes that are used before the root, e.g. prepay, reload, immature, unimportant, unwell, impossible, etc. Suffixes, on the contrary, are put after the stem, for example believable, footballer, perfectionist.

All of the words containing a stem and an affix or group of affixes are considered as derivatives or derived words. And this type of word formation is called affixation, because it requires the usage of affixes in the process of creating new word. [7, 41]

The number of derivatives is definitely great in the vocabulary of English (refrigerator, boiler, unnecessary). The only type of words that can compete with this type of structural words could be root words that have only one stem in their structure. The bright representatives of this classification can be original English root words or borrowings of earlier periods, such as mug, chair, kettle, bag, book, door, pen, egg, apple and etc. Moreover, English word stock is being enlarged thanks to words that are formed with the help of word-building – conversion. For instance, a book-to book, a handle-to handle, a turn-to turn etc. This type of word-formations mostly occurs in Modern English. [3, 48-49]

However this is not the only way of enriching word stock. There are several others such as compound words which consist of two or more roots like in dining-room, butterfly, father-in-law). This way of word formation is known as composition.

The somehow strange looking words as AIDS, gas, ads, adverts, apps, cam and etc. are considered as shortenings curtailed words or contractions. They are produced by more modern way of word building known as shortening. [1,78-104]

In the following article we are going to investigate some types of enriching English vocabulary stock and look through some classifications of word production.

So, what are main sources of enriching word stock in English language?

W o r d - F o r m a t i o n is the system of derived words and the procedure of forming new ones from the material attainable in the language following specific semantic and structural formulas and rules. For example, the noun **psychologist** is following the pattern v+-ist, that is a verbal stem +-the noun-forming suffix -ist. The meaning of the derived noun **psychologist** is related to the meaning of the stem **psychology**- ‘the science that studies human brain activities’ and the suffix **-ist** showing ‘an active doer’: a **psychologist** is ‘one who deals with psychology’.

The case is the same with other types of word formation as well. Taking an example of compound words combining two or more roots in order to create new meaning, we can see that they also obey quite strict structural and semantic regularities, as in the example of the roots of the word greenhouse we can see that it is following the adj+noun formula. And it can be obviously seen that the meaning of the whole derived word is also connected to the meanings of the constituent parts.

The structural devices with the connections to the meaning they refer to give an increase to regular new creations of derived words, as in the examples of runner, caretaker, babysitter or ice-

cream, long-term and so force.

In concordance with all semantic and structural types of words described above the following two general types of word-formation may be categorized, word-derivation and word-composition/compounding. From the point of word formation analysis words that are produced with the help of word-derivation possess solely one stem and one affix. For instance, friendship from friend, tiredness from tired, open-mindedness from open-minded, truthfulness from truthful and etc. But it should be noted that a certain number of words do not have affixes due to the fact that word building is achieved thanks to conversion. Words such as a look from to look, to bottle from a bottle, to dry from dry could be examples to it. Furthermore, from word derivation perspectives, conversion seems very interesting device as it does not require any change in form, only the word changes its semantic class (from noun to verb or vice versa.)

Words achieved by word-composition, on the contrary, have minimum two roots. For example, fingertips, Facebook, seasick, homesick and etc. [6, 55]

We should also take into consideration that types of word formation can be referred as to major and minor ways of creating words. As we mentioned above, the major ways of producing words in word derivation are affixation and conversion. We must also note that the notion of word-formation as explained above does not necessarily include semantic types of word-building such as shortenings, sound interchange and stress-interchange. These types traditionally belong to minor ways of word-formation. From the point of semantic word-building some professionals connote any semantic change in word-meaning, e.g. bark – 1) to make the characteristic short loud cry of a dog; 2) the tough exterior covering of a woody root or stem. Nevertheless, the vast majority of scientists consider this process only as a change in the semantic meaning of a word that can be reflected in homonyms. The application of the term word-formation to the process of semantic change and to the appearance of homonyms due to the development of polysemy seems to be debatable. [3,138-139]

Moreover, semantic change in the meaning of the word does not always necessarily result in the creation of a new word, so we cannot always classify it as a word formation device. Nor are we able to consider the process a word-formation device even in the case of real enrichment of the vocabulary achieved by creation of a line of homonyms. The production of homonyms is not a means of creating new words. It, actually, is the final result of a persistent and laborious process of semantic-development. Furthermore, there are not any means of word building following which homonyms can be made in the language. Lastly, integrating semantic development leads to separation of two or more independent meanings of the word, where the process of word-formation is defined by a certain sense interrelation between the new lexical unit and the source word. For the reasons mentioned above the cases of homonym, we think, should be treated as peculiar tool with the help of which word stock is enriched and it should be regarded as an equal means of word formation with other types. [11, 175]

From the perspective of their productivity, types of word formation can be regarded as two: productive, which actively participate in word production hitherto, and non-productive, which cannot form words now or have a very little impact. Let us take an example of affixation. It has been regarded as a productive way of word building ever since the Old English period. However, sound or stress interchange must have been a word-building tool once, yet in Modern English, as we have noted before, their current function is now only to imply the difference between various classes and forms of words. [9, 36-37]

Types of word formations follow certain derivational rules and derivational affixes that are easily recognised due to their ability of making new words which all who possess English can understand without any difficulties, to be exact according to their ability to produce so called nonce words or occasional words. This type requires that speakers combine such words when they are needed from the point of situation. That's why these words can be called as situational also. When in another situation the same word is needed again, they may combine them again. Such kinds of words are produced based on existing language material following certain patterns. There is no need to note that dictionaries do not necessarily possess the information about these words. [3, 108-114]

It is also should be noted that, the detention between productive and non-productive ways of word building, is not very friendly welcomed by all scholars working on lexicology. According to

some of the linguists, the borderline between these two issues need to be revised precisely one more time. They go by the idea that the distinction between the two notions is wrong a little. That is, in order to be considered as productive, types of word formation should be able to form unlimited numbers of words, and especially form occasional words easily. [2, 73]

Current studies, however, seem to confirm the ideas of the above given linguists, that the issue of productivity is pertinent from different angles. Furthermore, if in search for absolute productivity, one can fail in investigations that absolute productivity does not exist. That is, derivational affixes and patterns have various degrees of productivity. That's why it is essential that conditions assisting the productivity degree and the productivity of a certain pattern or affix should be distinguished. As almost all derivational means face both structural and semantic limitations, the productivity level will fall, i.e. the less the limitations, the higher is the degree of productivity, the bigger number of words are produced. There are basically two major limitations that are stuck to almost all word building types. First is the part of speech in which the derivational tool can function, and the second is the meaning stuck to it which delivers the regular meaningful interrelation between the two classes of words. It means that certain part of speech is distinguished by the set of affixes or patterns that form it. For example, er-noun producing suffix, un-, im-, in-, are the prefixes that add negative semantic connotation to the meaning of adjectives and sometimes verbs. [8, 27]

Tleumuratov considers word formation as the process of production of new words from the elements present in the language. There are certain structural patterns in every language. Words such as "teacher", "goalkeeper", "plumber", "director" and many others follow the structural pattern of word formation "V+er". According to him, word building can be investigated synchronically and diachronically. Synchronically we analyze those means of word formation which are common at the current day English linguistic system, whereas diachronically we look at the word formation system from the historical point of view. These two means of word production do not always necessarily coexist, but sometimes they do.

Ex. the word photography was originally compound: photo meaning image, grapho- to draw, fortnight - fēowertīene niht which mean 'fourteen nights'. But booth of these words has already lost their original two stem pattern and has become indispensable. The case is the same with return and turn. Historically these words had semantic correlations; analyzing them synchronically we may say that they have no interrelation. [5, 5-6]

Having analyzed synchronical means of word formation, one may conclude that affixation, conversion, word composition are considered as the most significant and the most productive ways of word formation. Other means of word production also exist such as backformation, sound interchange, shortening, blending. [10, 8-9]

Let us take the examples of sound interchange (grass-to graze, deep-depth) which was one of the most effective ways of word derivation in old English. Besides it can be essential object of study for a diachronic study, too. Even worse, sound interchange has already lost its significance in present-day English and no other new words can be formed by means of this type of word formatio. Affixation on the contrary, can be considered as productive both during the Old English and Modern English periods. [4, 26-28]

Tleumuratov agrees with the classification of Ginzburg and distinguishes between 2 means of word building: word composition and derived words. Specific features of derived words are that they have only one root and two or more affixes (suffixes or prefixes), as we mentioned above 'tiredness' from tired can be a good example of it. He also admits that sometimes new words are produced with the help of conversion, instead of derivation. Also he says composed words possess two or more roots. But interestingly, he also suggests that there are words achieved by derivation and composition. He calls them derivational compounds, loud-mouthed, long-lasting [5, 5-7]

But according to Dubenets there are four main ways of word formation, that can be considered as more suitable and covers bigger issue. He considers that word formation should be denoted as one of the most effective means of enlarging the word stock of a language, except the above mentioned main types of word building he adds abbreviations also to major types, including stress sound interchange, imitation, back formation and others to the secondary types. [6, 5]

Conclusion

As a conclusion, we may say that there are various ways of creating new notions and words in English language, such as word formation, derivation, composition, conversion, sound and stress interchange, affixation, blending, backformation and etc. according to their productivity they are considered as productive and non-productive, word formation being the most productive one.

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СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

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